

**BIR JINSLI TOR TEBRANISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI
YECHIMINI IFODALOVCHI DALAMBER FORMULASI**

Mingyasharova Sevara Abdulla qizi

Termiz muhandislik-texnologiya instituti o‘qituvchisi

Mamanov Jasur Hakim o‘g‘li

Termiz davlat universiteti 1-kurs magistri

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mexanika va fizikaning tebranish jarayonlari bilan bog‘liq bir qator masalalari giperbolik tipdagi tenglama bilan isodalanishi hamda tor tebranish tenglamasi uchun Koshi masalasining qo‘yilishi, Dalamber formulasi va uning fizikaviy talqini, Koshi masalasi yechimining turg‘unligi haqida qisqacha ma‘lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar. *Narrow oscillation equation, Dalamber formula, Cauchy problem, initial condition, generalized solution.*

**THE DALEMBERT FORMULA REPRESENTING THE SOLUTION OF THE
CAUCHY PROBLEM FOR A HOMOGENEOUS NARROW VIBRATION
EQUATION**

Abstract: *In this article, a number of problems of mechanics and physics related to vibrational processes can be solved by a hyperbolic type equation, as well as the introduction of the Cauchy problem for the narrow vibration equation, the Dalamber formula and its physical interpretation, and the stability of the solution of the Cauchy problem.*

Key words: *Information technology, methodology, knowledge, skills and abilities, multimedia.*

**ФОРМУЛА ДАЛАМБЕРА, ПРЕДСТАВЛЯЮЩАЯ РЕШЕНИЕ ЗАДАЧИ
КОШИ ДЛЯ ОДНОРОДНОГО УЗКОГО ВИБРАЦИОННОГО
УРАВНЕНИЯ**

Аннотатсия: *В данной статье ряд задач механики и физики, связанных с колебательными процессами, может быть решен уравнением гиперболического типа, а также введение задачи Коши для узкого уравнения колебаний, формулы Даламбера и ее физической интерпретации, а также устойчивость решения задачи Коши.*

Ключевые слова: *Уравнение узких колебаний, формула Даламбера, задача Коши, начальное условие, обобщенное решение.*

Koshi masalasining qo‘yilishida $\varphi_0(x)$, $\varphi_1(x)$ funksiyalarni yetarlicha silliq bo‘lsin deb talab qilib olsak va natijada bu funksiyalarning qaysi sinfga tegishli ekanligini aniqlab olamiz.

Agar $\varphi_0(x) \in C^2(\mathbb{R})^1$, $\varphi_1(x) \in C^1(\mathbb{R})^1$ bo‘lsa, u holda

$$u(x, t) = \frac{1}{2} [\varphi_0(x + at) + \varphi_0(x - at)] + \frac{1}{2a} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} \varphi_1(z) dz \quad (1)$$

formula bilan aniqlangan $u(x, t)$ funksiya $u_{tt} = a^2 u_{xx}$, $a = \text{const}$, Tor tebranish tenglamasini va $a(x, t)(dt)^2 - 2b(x, t)dtdx + c(x, t)(dx)^2 = 0$, boshlang‘ich shartlarni qanoatlantirishini bevosita tekshirib ishonch hosil qilishimiz mumkin.

Haqiqatdan ham (1) formulada $t = 0$ desak u holda

$$u(x, 0) = \varphi_0(x), \quad x \in R$$

bo‘ladi. (1) formuladan t bo‘yicha hosila olamiz

$$u_1 \frac{a\varphi_0'(x + at) - a\varphi_0'(x - at)}{2} + \frac{1}{2} [a\varphi_1(x + at) + \varphi_1(x - at)],$$

keyin $t = 0$ bo‘lganda

$$u_t(x, 0) = \varphi_1(x), \quad x \in R$$

ekanligini ko‘ramiz. Bu tor tebranish tenglamasi uchun Koshi masalasining yechimi mavjud ekanligini ko‘rsatadi. (1) formulani keltirib chiqarish tor tebranish tenglamasining

$$u(x, t) = f(x + at) + g(x - at), \quad (2)$$

umumiy yechimiga asoslangan va barcha bosqichlar bir qiymatli bajarildi. Shuning uchun yechimning yagonaligi esa uning qurish usulidan ham kelib chiqadi.

Koshi masalasi yechimining turg‘unligi.

Faraz qilaylik $u_0(x, t)$ funksiya $u_{tt} = a^2 u_{xx}$, $a = \text{const}$ tenglamaning

$$\text{quyidagi } u(x, 0) = \varphi_0^0(x), u_t(x, 0) = \varphi_1^0(x), \quad x \in R$$

Boshlang‘ich shartlarini qanoatlantiruvchi yechimi bo‘lsin .

Xuddi yuqoridagi kabi

$$u_0(x, 0) \text{ funksiya ham (1) formula orqali quriladi.}$$

Agar

$$|\varphi_0(x) - \varphi_0^0(x)| < \delta, \quad |\varphi_1(x) - \varphi_1^0(x)| < \delta, \quad \forall x \in R$$

Bo‘lsa, u holda $\forall x \in R, t \in [0, T], T$ ixtiyoriy musbat son uchun $u(x, t)$ va $u_0(x, t)$ yechimlarining ayirmasini baholaymiz.

$$\begin{aligned} |u(x, t) - u_0(x, t)| &\leq \frac{1}{2} |\varphi_0(x + at) - \varphi_0^0(x + at)| + \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} |\varphi_0(x - at) - \varphi_0^0(x - at)| + \frac{1}{2a} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} |\varphi_1(z) - \varphi_1^0(z)| dz < \\ &< \frac{1}{2} \delta + \frac{1}{2} \delta + \frac{1}{2a} \delta \int_{x-at}^{x+at} dz = \delta + \delta \frac{1}{2a} 2at = \delta(1 + t) < (1 + T), \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

Faraz qilaylik, ε ixtiyoriy musbat son va $\delta = \frac{\varepsilon}{1+T}$ bo'lsin.

U holda (3) tengsizlikdan $\forall \varepsilon > 0$ son uchun shunday $\delta = \frac{\varepsilon}{1+T}$ son topiladiki, barcha $x \in R$ va $t \in [0, T]$ larda

$$|\varphi_0(x) - \varphi_0^0(x)| < \delta, \quad |\varphi_1(x) - \varphi_1^0(x)| < \delta$$

shartlar bajirilganda $|u(x, t) - u_0(x, t)| < \varepsilon$ tengsizlik o'rinli bo'ladi.

Bundan, tor tebranish tenglamasi uchun Koshi masalasining yechimi berilganlarga uzluksiz bo'g'liq ekanligi kelib chiqadi [1, 445].

TEOREMA. Agar $\varphi_0(x) \in C^2(R)^1$, $\varphi_1(x) \in C^1(R)^1$ bo'lsa, u holda tor tebranish tenglama uchun Koshi masalasining yechimi mavjud, yagona va turg'un bo'ladi, ya'ni

$$u_{tt} = a^2 u_{xx}, \quad a = \text{const},$$

$$u(x, 0) = \varphi_0(x), \quad u_t(x, 0) = \varphi_1(x), \quad -\infty < x < +\infty$$

masalaning $u(x, t)$ yechimi (1) formula bilan aniqlanadi.

Ma'lum bir masalalarni yechishda $\varphi_0(x)$, $\varphi_1(x)$ funksiyalar teoremaning shartlarini bajarmasligi mumkin. Bunda tor tebranish tenglamasi uchun

$$u_{tt} = a^2 u_{xx}, \quad a = \text{const},$$

$$u(x, 0) = \varphi_0(x), \quad u_t(x, 0) = \varphi_1(x), \quad -\infty < x < +\infty$$

Koshi masalasining regulyar yechimi tushunchasini kiritib bo'lmaydi.

Bunday hollarda umumlashgan yechim tushunchasi kiritiladi.

TA'RIF. Tor tebranish tenglamasi uchun $u_{tt} = a^2 u_{xx}$, $a = \text{const}$,

$$u(x, 0) = \varphi_0(x), \quad u_t(x, 0) = \varphi_1(x), \quad -\infty < x < +\infty$$

masalasining umumlashgan yechimi deb, $u_{tt} = a^2 u_{xx}$, $a = \text{const}$ tenglamaning

$$u(x, 0) = \varphi_0(x), \quad u_t(x, 0) = \varphi_1(x), \quad -\infty < x < +\infty,$$

boshlang'ich shartlarini qanoatlantiruvchi $u_n(x, t)$ regulyar yechimlarning tekis yaqinlashuvchi ketma-ketligining liminti bo'lgan $u(x, t)$ funksiyaga aytiladi.

Bu yerda $\varphi_{n0}(x) \in C^2(R)^1$, $\varphi_{n1}(x) \in C^1(R)^1$ va bu funksiyalar sonlar o'qining ixtiyoriy $[\alpha, \beta]$ segmentida $\varphi_0(x)$ va $\varphi_1(x)$ funksiyalarga tekis yaqinlashuvchi ketma-ketliklar, ya'ni

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \varphi_{n0}(x) \rightrightarrows \varphi_0(x), \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \varphi_{n1}(x) \rightrightarrows \varphi_1(x).$$

Agar $\varphi_0(x)$, $\varphi_{n1}(x) \in C(R^1)$ bo'lsa, u holda $u_{tt} = a^2 u_{xx}$, $a = \text{const}$, $u(x, 0) = \varphi_0(x)$, $u_t(x, 0) = \varphi_1(x)$, $-\infty < x < +\infty$ Koshi masalasining umumlashgan yechimi mavjud, yagona va (1) formula bilan ifodalanishini ko'rsatish qiyin emas [2, 432].

Xulosa qilib aytish mumkinki, Mexanika va fizikaning tebranish jarayonlari bilan bog'liq bir qator muammolari, masalan, tor va membrananing tebranishi, gaz, elektromexanik to'lqinlarning tarqalishi kabi jarayonlar giperbolik tipdagi tenglamalar orqali ifodalanadi. Shuning uchun ham ushbu maqolada bir jinsli tor tebranish tenglamasi uchun koshi masalasi yechimini ifodalovchi D'alamber formulasi

keltirilgan. Koshi masalasining turg'unligi va uning qo'yilishi haqida qisqacha ma'lumotlar berib o'tilgan.

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